

2-Hydroxy-5-Chloro Acetophenone Oxime as a Gravimetric Reagent for Oxo-Vanadium(V)

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Oxo-vanadium(V) has been precipitated quantitatively from the solution in the pH range 3.5-6.5 with 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone oxime and determined by weighing the complex VO(OH)(C₈H₇ClNO₂)₂ after drying at 110-120°. The reagent has been used in the separation and gravimetric determination of vanadium(V) in its binary mixture with copper. The interference due to other ions has been avoided either using suitable masking agent or by working at controlled pH. I. R. spectral studies have also been carried out to assign a tentative structure to the complex.

A series of oxo-vanadium complexes of a variety of co-ordinating ligands have been reported in the literature¹⁻⁶. Only a few organic reagents are known for gravimetric estimation of vanadium in which vanadium is directly weighed as the complex. In other cases it is determined as its pentavalent oxide. Cupferron⁶⁻⁷ suffers from the disadvantages that the vanadium cupferronate starts decomposing even at a low temperature as 70°. In case of 8-hydroxy quinoline⁸⁻⁹, vanadium(V) forms precipitates of variable composition and therefore, it is weighed as V₂O₅ after ignition. In the precipitation of silver vanadate¹⁰, strict control of pH is necessary as stoichiometry of the precipitate is pH dependent. Mercurous vanadate¹¹ on ignition gives toxic mercury fumes.

The reagent 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone oxime (HCAO) precipitates vanadium as a complex of definite stoichiometry (1 : 2) which can be directly weighed with out ignition to the pentavalent oxide. This is the chief advantage of this reagent over the usual methods. It has also been possible to determine gravimetrically vanadium and copper when present together in the same solution satisfactorily taking advantage of the different pH range for precipitation.

Experimental

The reagent (HCAO) was prepared by Fries¹² migration of *p*-chlorophenyl acetate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. It was then converted into oxime by refluxing it with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate in dilute alcohol. The product was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 185°.

Sodium vanadate (NaVO₃·H₂O) (Riedel) was dissolved in double distilled water to prepare the vanadium(V) solution. It was standardised gravimetrically using mercurous nitrate method¹³.

Procedure :

A known volume of the oxo-vanadium(V) solution was taken in a 400 ml beaker and diluted to 100 ml. An excess (two fold) of the ethanolic solution of the reagent was then added. The pH was adjusted to 3.5 to 6.5 with hydrochloric acid and ammonium hydroxide. The reddish yellow complex was digested on a water bath for about 40 minutes. It was filtered while hot, through a sintered glass crucible (G-4) and washed with hot water and finally several times with 50% hot ethanol. The precipitate was dried at 110-120° to a constant weight. The results of some of the estimations in the pH range 3.5 to 6.5 are recorded in Table-1.

The results of 30 estimations of vanadium over a pH range 4.0-5.5 revealed that 1.86 mg of vanadium could be determined accurately. The conversion factor (vanadium/vanadium complex) being 0.1124.

The complex is not affected by dilute acids and alkalis. It dissolves in conc. HNO₃ and H₂SO₄. The complex is soluble in dioxane, chloroform, nitrobenzene and carbon tetrachloride and insoluble in ethanol.

The thermolysis curve of vanadium complex has a horizontal portion extending upto 170°, above 170° the complex decomposes rapidly upto 185°, thereafter there is a gradual loss in weight due to slow decomposition of the complex and a sudden loss in weight is observed at 490°.

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TABLE—1 ESTIMATION OF VANADIUM(V) IN THE pH RANGE 3.5-6.5
Amount of Vanadium taken = 7.45 mg.

S. No.	pH of the solution	Weight of the complex in mg.	Vanadium found in mg.	Error %
1.	3.5	66.0	7.42	-0.40
2.	4.0	66.2	7.44	-0.13
3.	4.5	66.2	7.44	-0.13
4.	5.0	66.2	7.44	-0.13
5.	5.5	66.2	7.44	-0.13
6.	6.5	66.4	7.46	+0.13

Effect of foreign ions on precipitation :

The interference due to salts of foreign ions was removed in most of the cases by working at controlled pH values. Vanadium has been determined satisfactorily at pH range 3.5-6.5 in presence of Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, CH₃COO⁻, SO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻, B₄O₇²⁻, tartrate and citrate. The ions Cd(II), Se(IV), Te(IV), Ni(II), Co(II), Th(IV), Zr(IV) and Mo(VI) do not interfere at pH 4.0. The interference due to Fe(III) was removed by adding tartrate. The ions e.g. E.D.T.A., IO₃⁻, F⁻, Cu(II) and oxotitanium (IV) have been found to interfere.

Separation and determination of Vanadium (V) and Cu(II) :

When vanadium and copper were present in a binary mixture, copper was precipitated first at pH 2.5 with the reagent. The mixture of the two ions was taken in the beaker (400 ml.) and diluted to 150 ml. It was warmed to 35-40° and an excess (two fold) of the reagent solution was added with constant stirring. The buff coloured precipitate was digested on a water bath at a temperature of 70-80° for about half an hour, allowed to stand for two hours and filtered through a sintered glass crucible (C-4). The complex was washed with slightly warmed water and finally several times with 20% warm ethanol. It was then dried at 110-120° to constant weight. The conversion factor (copper/copper complex) is 0.1468. Molar composition of the complex is Cu(C₈H₇Cl NO₂)₂.

The filtrate containing oxo-vanadium(V) was evaporated to about 100 ml. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.5. The vanadium was precipitated and determined gravimetrically as described above. Results of some of the estimations are recorded in Table-2.

Structure of the complex :

The vanadium complex was analysed for its carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents to determine its composition. The composition of the complex corresponds to the formula VO(OH)(C₈H₇Cl NO₂)₂ in which vanadium to ligand ratio is 1 : 2 (Found C, 41.88 ; H, 3.21 ; N, 6.41 Calcd. C, 42.40 ; H, 3.33 ; N, 6.16%).

The normal oximes¹⁴⁻¹⁷ have I.R. absorption bands at 3300 cm⁻¹-3150 cm⁻¹ (OH str.) 1690-1510 (C=N str.) and around 950 cm⁻¹ (N-O str.). In the present investigation the ligand 2-hydroxy-5-chloro acetophenone oxime has shown prominent bands at 2740 cm⁻¹, 1587 cm⁻¹ and 971 cm⁻¹ assignable to intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH, C=N and N-O str. frequencies which are in good agreement with the results obtained by Palm and Werbin¹⁸. The broad weak band at 2740 cm⁻¹ due to intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH in the reagent is not observed in the complex under investigation. The band due to phenolic C-O vibrations at 1266 cm⁻¹ is observed at 1299 cm⁻¹ in the complex. These observations suggest that the hydroxyl group of the ligand has taken part in the bond formation.

The C=N str. at 1587 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand is found at 1493 cm⁻¹ in the complex can be interpreted as a consequence of the coordination through nitrogen of the metal ion.

The band due to V=O and OH in the complex appears at 990 cm⁻¹ and 3500 cm⁻¹ respectively.

TABLE—2

S. No.	Metal taken in mg.		Complex in mg.		Metal found in mg.		Error %	
	Cu	V	Cu	V	Cu	V	Cu	V
1.	9.40	7.45	64.00	66.20	9.39	7.44	-0.05	-0.13
2.	9.40	14.90	64.00	132.60	9.39	14.90	-0.05	-0.00
3.	14.10	7.45	96.00	66.20	14.09	7.44	-0.07	-0.13
4.	14.10	14.90	95.80	132.60	14.06	14.90	-0.28	-0.00
5.	18.80	14.90	127.80	132.60	18.76	14.90	-0.21	-0.00

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